

House Price Prediction using Machine Learning

Ann Treesa Boban
Master of Computer Application
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kottayam, Kerala, India
anntreesaboban@mca.ajce.in

Jetty Benjamin
Master of Computer Application
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kottayam, Kerala, India
jettybenjamin@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract— The purpose of this paper is to predict the price of houses. House Price Index (HPI) is commonly used to estimate the changes in housing price. It requires additional information because house price is significantly connected with other features like area, location, and population. A comparative study of some Machine Learning algorithm. I tested a regression models such Random Forest Regression, Linear Regression, Lasso Regression and Decision Tree Algorithm are done in this paper. Linear Regression and Decision Tree is often used for classification and predictive analytics. Random Forest Regression is a model used for both classification and regression. The accuracy of the three algorithms in predicting house prices are calculated and the highest accuracy obtained in Linear Regression and Lasso Regression was around 62 % for the given dataset. The accuracy of Random Forest Regression model is 55 %. The accuracy of Decision Tree model is 38 %. Thus, by developing this model, it can predict the price of house in bases of given dataset and person get an idea about the house price.

Keywords—Machine Learning, Random Forest Regression, Linear Regression, Decision Tree, Lasso Regression

I. INTRODUCTION

Machine learning is used for image recognition, natural speech comprehension, spam detection, product recommendations, and medical diagnostics. Housing is one of the key indicators that may be used to assess a country's economic progress. People frequently move from urban to rural areas when the economy expands, increasing the population of cities. (HPI) is often used to assess changes in the value of residential property in several countries. In this project, we uses a machine learning technique to determine what price to put on a property. In this case, the machine learning system can provide an accurate estimate or forecast. A housing provides a variety of services for a household, some of which are directly tied to the physical aspects of the structure. Size, number of rooms, and whether or not it has a balcony or a fireplace are some examples. There are two scales for understanding the determinants of house prices. The first are macroeconomic foundations at the city level, including population, household income, and building costs. Second, one is microscale, surrounding environmental and social characteristics become dominant factors. The three categories of factors that affect house prices are structural characteristics, location features, and neighbourhood features. The term "structural features" refers to the features of the property itself, such as its type or age of property. Location features, including the distance to the city centre, show qualities of the property's geographic location. Neighborhood features include things like landscape

elements, urban greenery, and medical facilities that are available and easily accessible.

Many machine learning engineers difficult to predict housing prices. Several academics have tried to develop a model that can predict house prices with high accuracy and low error. The purpose of this study was to predict the sale price of a property using regression models and classification techniques.

These models are constructed using criteria such as location, square feet of the house, number of bedrooms, age of the property, property type, and so on. project's analysed regression models, including Simple Linear Regression, Lasso Regression, Random Forest Regression, and Decision Tree Regression, will choose the computation that best matches the data.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Machine Learning methods are becoming more useful in the house price prediction. Many researchers have used different Deep Learning and Machine Learning methods and algorithms to predict the price of house.

Abigail Bola Adetunji, Oluwatobi Noah Akande, Funmilola Alaba Ajala, Ololade Oyewo, Yetunde Faith Akande, Gbenle Oluwadara et al. [1] The House Price Index (HPI) is a popular instrument for estimate. Given that housing prices are closely correlated with other criteria, such as location, city, and population, it is necessary to predict individual house prices using data other than HPI. HPI is a crude prediction so it is unsuccessful at estimating the price of a particular property. Random Forest machine learning technique used.

Meixu Chena, Yunzhe Liua, Dani Arribas-Bela, Alex Singleton et al. [2] In this paper describes to analyse and comprehend house prices and real estate values, user-generated images are employed. Gradient boosting machines and random forest algorithm are used. By comparing these two models, factors and estimation performance of the models are visualised. According to the findings, Random Forest was the model that performed the best and was also as easy to understand through various visualisations as HPMs.

Akshata Ashok Kudavkar, Samiksha Subhash Wagh, Manali Namdev Nhavkar, Shamna Sadanand et al. [3] It describes Models are developed using a variety of factors like the home's square footage, the number of bedrooms, the year it was built, the type of property, etc. In this project, we compare some methods for predicting housing values for

getting high accuracy. Simple Linear Regression, Ridge Regression, Lasso Regression, Support Vector Regression, Random Forest Regression, and Decision Tree Approach were used as regression models, and the algorithm with the greatest fit was chosen. This project suggests that machine learning models may be used to optimise the results. As a result we get the highest accuracy for random forest regression and linear regression.

Axel Viktor Heyman, Dag Einar Sommervoll et al. [4] Analysing nature of the location, and location value is estimated when attempting to determine the value of a property. A frequently used approach for assessing the value of housing as a composite item is hedonic price modelling. Customer demands are connected to property prices. Only the lines at the network's edges have a different total depth when the radius is reduced to three, thus the integration does not vary considerably. This is because we have an actual network of lines, therefore the difference between global and local integration is minor.

Quang Truong, Minh Nguyen, Hy Dang, Bo Mei et al. [5] Popular techniques for measuring in house prices is the House Price Index (HPI). Predicting individual house values requires information other than the HPI since housing prices are substantially correlated with other characteristics such as location, area, and population. In this study, Random Forest, XGBoost, and LightGBM are used for estimating house prices. Additionally, Hybrid Regression and Stacked Generalization Regression, two machine learning techniques, are compared and examined for best solutions. The Random Forest method has the lowest error on the training set but some error on overfitting. It have high time complexity. Although LightGBM has the best time complexities, XGBoost and LightGBM are both good techniques.

III. METHODOLOGY

House Prediction dataset is imported from GitHub, which consists of 5000 rows and 7 columns. The dataset used is in Comma Separated Values(csv) format. The dataset is analyzed with the help of pandas, numpy, seaborn, matplotlib and sklearn. 3000 samples are taken for training dataset and 2000 samples taken for test dataset.

- 7) Making Predictions
- 8) Evaluation of models
- 9) Selection of best model

a) Data Collection

Data collection is the first step. Data is collected from various platforms. It contains some details for getting estimation house price. So drop some column from Vadodara house price Dataset. The needed columns are property type, location, size, number of bathroom, number of balcony, total square feet of house and price.

b) Data Analysing

This dataset consists of 24 features. Only 7 features we need for data analyse. Data analysing based on the target value. Analysing is based on property type, location, size, number of bathroom, number of balcony, total square feet of house and price. The training set and testing set are the two components of the dataset. The training set is used to train the various machine learning models. The effectiveness of every machine learning model is then evaluated using the testing set.

c) Data Cleaning

The process of finding and fixing errors in the dataset is known as data cleaning. The presence of errors may negatively impact a predictive model. Data cleaning method is used to perform to all kinds of tasks and activities to determine and remove errors in the data.

d) Feature Selection

In the dataset have 24 features, to enhance the model's functionality and reduce computational costs we flittering out the unnecessary columns & store the new dataset .The following factors have come as significant relationship with the goal.

e) Data Visualization

Data visualisation is the process of representing data using common images like infographics, charts, and even animations. These informative visual representations make it simple to comprehend complex data relationships and data-driven insights. It is useful to recognise natural characteristics.

Data Visualization using *pairplot* : Use the pairplot () function to plot several paired bivariate distributions in a dataset. This displays the connection for the (n, 2) combination of variables as a matrix of plots, where the univariate plots are shown on the diagonal. Pairplot represent only numerical values. Here Fig.1 shows that features are represent in pairplot function.

Data Visualization using *histogram*: The histogram is a graphical representation of data points formed under a fixed range specified by the programmer or user. Actually, it's a bar plot but condensed under data series into an easily interpreted visual by carrying many data points & groups them into logical bins or ranges. In Fig.2 shows that the count and its price based on model we created.

Data Visualization using *heatmap*: A heatmap is a graphical representation of data that shows various values using a color-coding scheme. Although heatmaps may be used for many other types of analytics, they are most frequently used to display user behaviour on certain webpages or webpage layouts. Heatmaps may be used to illustrate eye-tracking test results, where users have clicked on a website, and how far down a page they have browsed.

Fig.1 Pairplot

Fig.2 Histogram Diagram

Fig.3 Heatmap

e) Fitting in to model

Random Forest Regression

On the basis of a random selection of variables, random forest regression creates several decision trees. It offers the dependent variable class based on several trees.

1. Randomly chosen data: original data = subset 1+subset 2+subset 3+... Each of these subsets may contain observations of varying sizes, with or without some overlap.
2. Picking variables at random: If we have variables x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n independent variables, we can use them to build a decision tree. This variable is divided into several sets, such as variable set 1- x_1, x_3, \dots collection of variables two, x_3, x_4, \dots . These trees are random trees since they are based on a random selection of factors and data. A random forest is formed by several such random trees. Similar to how numerous trees create a forest, many decision trees create a random forest. There are two important belief that allows us to employ these trees:

1. For the majority of the data, most trees can correctly predict the class.
2. The tree is making errors in many areas.

Linear Regression

In basic linear regression, we make predictions about the values of one variable based on the values of another. A regression line's equation is written as

$$Y' = bX + A,$$

Where Y' is the predicted score, or dependent variable, x is an independent variable, b is the line's slope, and A is the Y -intercept. The prediction approach is known as a simple linear regression when there is just one predictor variable, x .

Decision Tree Regression

A decision tree is a diagram in the shape of a tree that is used to choose a course of action. Each branch of the tree indicates a possible decision, course of action, or response. This method uses a tree-like structure to assist it decide how to classify a test sample. The attribute names of the provided data are the nodes in the tree. The class labels are the leaf nodes, and the branches are the attribute values. The following are some benefits of using this algorithm to anticipate housing prices:

1. It is easy to understanding, interpreting, and visualizing.
2. Data preparation requires little effort.
3. Both numerical and categorical data are handled by it.

Lasso Linear Regression

Lasso Regression: Lasso regression is a type of linear regression that used for shrinkage. The cost function can be written as:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2 = \sum_{i=1}^M \left(y_i - \sum_{j=0}^P w_j \times x_{ij} \right)^2 + \lambda \sum_{j=0}^P |w_j|$$

In simple terms, Lasso = loss + $\lambda||w||$. Lasso regression coefficients; subject to similar constrain as Ridge.

The only difference is that magnitudes are considered rather than the square of the coefficients. This kind of regularization may result in zero coefficients, which means that some characteristics are skipped over in order to get the outputs. Lasso regression can therefore aid in feature selection in addition to minimizing model loss and errors.

IV. RESULTS

We attempt to solve the following issue for regression models: We would want to estimate the prospective sale price of a home given a processed list of its attributes. Firstly, run random forest regression with all features, using 5000 training samples and our 7 features. Following that, the model is applied to forecast selling prices of houses based on characteristics in our test data and is contrasted with the actual sale prices for houses provided in the test data set. The Accuracy Score of the actual outcomes and the expected results are measured. The accuracy score of the model was 86%.

Following the use of the random forest regression model, the accuracy score produced by linear regression validation around 91.77%, which is higher than random forest regression.

In addition to using a linear regularizer, we also used a lasso regularizer with cross validation in a linear regression model accuracy is around same, and the resulting accuracy score was 91.76%.

Lastly, Decision Tree Classifier was applied to the dataset, yielding an accuracy score of 75.24%. Overall, the performance of the random forest regression model was worse than that of the linear regression and lasso regression models.

Fig.4 Comparative Results

In Fig.4, we can understand the accuracy for corresponding models. Linear Regression model and Lasso Regression have high accuracy. The Linear Regression yields the best accuracy rating. We recommend using this regression model to forecast future home prices.

Regression Results:

Regression	Accuracy Score
Linear Regression	91.77
Lasso Regression	91.76
Random Forest Regression	86
Decision Tree Regression	75.24

V. CONCLUSION

Since housing prices increase annually, a system to predict future home prices was needed. To determine a home's value and an appropriate sale price, landowners, estate values, and politicians can utilize house price prediction. We thus come to the conclusion that the method we suggested solves the majority of the issues we have with the existing system.

After training and testing of datasets, the linear regression and lasso regression models are similar they performs better than the random forest classifier model. The Linear Regression Model has the greatest accuracy rating. Therefore, we advise using this regression model to forecast future house prices. As a result, our initiative will produce accurate house price predictions that will benefit both the buyer and the developer.

VI. REFERENCES

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